

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

Ogheneakoke, Edore Clifford (Ph.D.)

Department of Social Science Education, Delta State University, Abraka; Nigeria

ABSTRACT: The study examined the impact of cybercrime on the learning outcomes of Social Studies undergraduates. Correlational research design was the study design. Eighty (80) Social Studies students were utilised for the study. Two (2) research instruments (Students academic and (questionnaire) were employed to generate the study data. The data gathered were analysed and presented in tables. The Pearson Products Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions, while regression statistics was utilised for the hypotheses testing. The study established that there is a significant relationship between cybercrime and students' learning outcomes of Social Studies undergraduates; there is a significant association between cyber-crime and unemployment. It was recommended that the government should provide youth empowerment as a solution to unemployment, government should implement cyber security best practices, especially in the financial sector, security software should be installed on personal devices and universities should introduce cyber security as a compulsory course.

KEYWORDS: Cyber; impact of cybercrime; Crime, Learning Outcomes, Social Studies Undergraduates, Delta State University.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the World Wide Web technology in 1993, known as "Yahoo E-mail," was welcomed with joy world over because it served as a tool that facilitated speedy and easy communication around the world. Crime appears to be a permanent feature of modern society. In spite of the efforts of social workers, law enforcement agencies, and personal and criminal justice professionals to minimize it, the world/universe is becoming a more terrible place, where crimes such as cybercrime are the order of the day (Aransiola & Asindemade, 2011).

Cybercrime, as defined by Onyema, Ogechukwu and Anthonia (2019), is a crime committed with phones and a computer through a communication device or a transmission medium referred to as the "cyberspace" and a global network called the "internet." He notes that cybercrime has been complexity and costs have been going up since corporations, governments, individuals, or People all over the world started using computers to do business.. Khan, Akram, Munir and Almas (2021) defines cybercrime as any criminal offenses committed using the internet or another computer network as a component of the crime. Akogwo (2018) explained that cyber-crimes constitute offenses done against individuals or groups of individuals with a criminal motive to intentionally harm the reputation of the victim or cause physical or mental harm to the victim directly or using indirect modern communication networks such as the internet and mobile devices/phones; such crimes may threaten the nation's security and financial health. Cybercrime is now committed by people of all ages, from young to old, but most often by undergraduates (Adesina, 2017).

The term "yahoo-yahoo" is a well-known term that is also called maga, sakawa, "G-boys," VIP Export, mugu client, and Scammers. Brain Box of the Internet, Bank Cleaner, etc, (Monsurat, 2020). Yahoo-Yahoo is among the cyber-crimes that disparaged the integrity of Nigerians both home and abroad, especially in the global/world criminal report. The scourge of this crime was predominantly endemic in Nigeria as a result of widespread internet accessibility. The utilization of the internet, made it easier for swindlers and importers to hypnotize their clients, known as "maga," with strategies to become cyber-crime victims. Even though some scholars believe that there is a particular logic that Yahoo and Yahoo! implement to defraud people, yet this research argues that their strategies change like a frame of fire every day. However, this 21st century bystander heard different reports of Yahoo-Yahoo scams and fraudulent cases as an international and global phenomenon, which, as a result, tainted Nigeria as the most corrupt and fraudster-enhancing country in the world (Monsurat, 2020). As a result of this, Osuji and Amadi (2020) emphasized that Nigeria has been fashioned as the origin of the most fraudulent spam most likely to appear in cyberspace.

Edeoghon and Mobote (2020) observed that a sizeable number of cyber criminals in Nigeria are undergraduate students. They have discovered different ways of using the internet to do different types of criminal activities. Hence, Asadu (2021) noted

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

that cybercrime can be said to be on the increase in the country due to a lack of security awareness and underreporting, respectively. Frank (2019) observed that Cybercrime has become a major channel. in Nigeria for pilfering money and conducting business espionage. According to him, Nigeria is ranked sixth in globally in terms of cyber-attacks and vulnerabilities. In Nigeria and around the world, Nigerians have a reputation for being among the most prolific offenders of cybercrime. In comparison to citizens of other nations, a significantly higher proportion of Nigerians are reported to have been apprehended by broadcasting stations for engaging in dishonest acts.

According to Akinyetun, Adewale, Oke, Samuel and Abiodun (2021), cyber-crime has become the new normal and is having a significant impact on the financial industry; every day, crimes are committed against leading companies that were thought to have top security protocols in place. It continues to have a serious financial impact on the economy. Cybercrime has been an elusive factor. in the cyberspace transaction in Nigeria, where cybercrimes and computer-related crimes are endemic. With the integration of computer technology as a global issue, the economy of the majority of nations in the world is accessible through the utilisation of information and communication technology and is at stake with the opportunity opened to the general public in use for viable objectives, certain high-level crimes are committed, and some of those responsible for the crime are referred to as "yahoo boys." (Monsurat, 2020). They represent themselves as having particular goods to sell or that they are involved in shaping or in a loan scheme. They falsely present documents and tell all sorts of lies to get money or claim to be the beneficiaries of the thousands of United States dollars in a trust account (Wahab, 2017).

Adesina (2017) believes that there are many graduates who excel in their various studies but are still out on the job market for years, until they catch up with cyber criminals with luxurious and valuable property. According to Okeshola and Adeta (2013), one of the problems with cybercrime in Nigeria is that there are no jobs, and those that are available are taken by the children of the elites and connected people. A problem that affects economies all around the world is unemployment, which is widely recognized as the primary driver of poverty. The youth are considered the formulation for a nation's future growth and sustainable development; they are the key agents for social change, economic development, and technological innovations (Adeleke, 2017). Hence, the failure of leadership at all levels in Nigeria to promote positive values for the youth has often translated into social incongruence.

Nigerian undergraduates appear to have developed a spirit of fear of the future in that they think of fast ways to break through financial bounds once they have graduated. As a result, they negatively engage in sharp cybercrime practices, to be specific, in order to meet their life expectancies (Agba, 2013). As predicted, the nation's youth, as the leaders of tomorrow, will soon experience a flow that will have an impact on academic life. Student behavior also plays a major role in academic performance. The behaviour and actions of a student can have an impact not only on her own capacity to learn but also on the circumstances in which other students learn (Atubi & Obro, 2020). The effects that the behaviours of students can have on the ability to maintain a high level of instructional effectiveness are referred to as behavioural learning outcomes, commonly associated with being a good student, including arriving ready to work, regularly attending classes, paying attention and participating in class, and devoting time to study and completing homework (Obro, 2020, Akinyetun, Adewale, Oke, Samuel & Abiodun, 2021).

A study carried out by Adegbola and Fadara (2022) indicated that cybercrime instigates bad behavior in students. In his study, he observed that the affected student did not have time for academic activities such as coming late to class, refusing to do their assignment, or studying. The study concluded that cybercrime has a negative influence on students' performance; hence, the outcome is examination malpractice, a low grade, and school dropout. Hence, this study looked at the impact of cybercrime on the learning outcomes of Social Studies undergraduates.

RQs

1. Is there relationship between cybercrime and students learning outcomes?
2. Is there association between unemployment and cybercrime?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between cybercrime and students learning outcome.
2. There is no significant association between unemployment and cybercrime.

METHOD

The survey descriptive design was used in this study. The study population comprised of eighty (80) Social Studies students at Delta State University, Abraka. The study sample comprised of all eighty (80) students using the judgmental sampling techniques. The study instrument was the questionnaire. It was divided into two parts (A and B). Part A contained respondent personal data, while Part B contained 15 items. A four-point scale was used to rank respondent responses, which includes: SA = 4, A=3, D=2 and SD=1. Research questions were answered using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) while hypotheses were tested using linear and multiple linear regression. Decisions were made at 0.05 level of significance.

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

RESULTS

RQ1: Is there relationship between cybercrime and student learning outcomes?

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) analysis of cybercrime and student learning outcomes.

Variables	N	r	Decision
Cybercrime	80	0.576	Positive Relationship
Student Learning Outcomes	80		

Table 1 summarised the analysis of data relating to cybercrime and student learning outcomes. The result ($r = 0.576$) indicated a positive correlation in cyber-crime and student learning outcomes. Thus, it can be concluded that the relationship between cyber-crime and student learning outcomes exist.

RQ2: Is there association between unemployment and cybercrime?

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) analysis of Unemployment and Cybercrime.

Variables	N	r	Decision
Unemployment	300	0.444	Positive relationship
Cybercrime	300		

Table 2 summarised the analysis of data relating to unemployment and cybercrime. The correlation results ($r = 0.444$) indicated an association between unemployment and cybercrime. Thus, in conclusion, there exist an association between unemployment and cybercrime. To conclude on the observed correlation, hypothesis 2 was tested for significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between cybercrime and students learning outcome.

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis of cybercrime and students learning outcome.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3.623	1	3.623	254.132	.000 ^b
Residual	4.222	88	.016		
Total	7.372	89			

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.757	.046		16.843	.000
cyber-crime and student learning outcomes	.242	.016	.576	14.434	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = .576^a$, $R\text{-Square} = .479$

a. Dependent Variable: Students Learning Outcome

b. Predictors: (Constant), Cyber-crime

Table 3 shows a regression analysis of cyber-crime and student learning outcomes $F(1, 88) = 254.132$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is, therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between cyber-crime and student learning outcomes. The table further indicated that the unstandardised regression coefficients (B), show how much the dependent variable (student learning outcomes) varies with the independent variable when all other independent variables (Cybercrime) are held constant. Thus, the higher the B-value, the greater the influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. cyber-crime and student learning outcomes with an unstandardised regression coefficient (B) value of 0.242 and a standardised regression coefficient (Beta) value of 0.576 was reported to have a significant relationship with student learning outcomes.

H₀₁: There is no significant association between unemployment and cybercrime.

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

Table 2: Linear Regression Analysis of Teacher Use of Instructional Supervision and Quality Social Studies Teaching in Upper Basic Classes in Delta State.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	3.127	1	3.127	219.688	.000 ^b
Residual	4.666	88	.016		
Total	7.366	89			

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.789	.052		17.664	.000
Unemployment	.267	.016	.444	16.442	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$, $R = .444^a$, $R\text{-Square} = .512$

a. Dependent Variable: Cyber-crime

b. Predictors: (Constant), Unemployment.

Table 2 provides the R and R² values. The R-value represents a simple correlation and is 0.444, which indicates a correlation. The R² value indicates how much of the total variation in the dependent variable, cyber-crime, can be explained by the independent variable. In this case, 0.512 51.2% can be explained, which is very large showed that unemployment accounted for 51.2% of cyber-crime.

The result also shows a regression analysis of unemployment and cyber-crime $F(1, 89) = 219.688$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is, therefore rejected. This implies that there is a significant association between unemployment and cyber-crime. The table further indicates that the unstandardised regression coefficients (B), show how much the dependent variable (cyber-crime) varies with an independent variable when all other independent variables (Unemployment) are held constant. Thus, the higher the B-value, the greater the influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. Unemployment with an unstandardised regression coefficient (B) value of 0.267 and a standardised regression coefficient (Beta) value of 0.444 was reported to have a significant association with cyber-crime.

DISCUSSION

The result of hypothesis one indicates that there is a significant relationship between cybercrime and students' learning outcomes. The findings suggest that Cybercrime has evolved into a cancer. in the Nigerian school system. Many forms of it exist, from gambling to identity theft. The use of technologically advanced equipment in the classroom should make lessons easier to understand for students. Students' senses are stimulated, their attention is captured and held, and their minds are kept on the task at hand in the classroom when using a smart gadget. In this particular case study, it's the other way around. In point of fact, it's a tool that gets in the way of effective learning. These findings are consistent with those of previous studies that have found a link between cybercrime and student performance, including those by Lin and Chiang (2017), Igba, Igba, Nwambam, et al. (2018), Ajayi (2019), and Adegbola and Fadara (2022). This is a fact, as students today are more likely to use their computers and mobile phones to commit cyber-crime than to utilize the internet to research academic topics in an e-library. Exam cheating, dropping out of school, and poor scores are just some of the ways in which cyber-crime negatively impacts education.

The result from hypothesis two shows there is a significant association between cyber-crime and unemployment. The country's alarmingly high unemployment rate has the potential to be a source of suffering. The problem is especially complex regarding crime among Nigerian youth. Statistics indicated that every young citizen in the country is officially unemployed This finding agrees with the findings of Al-Barashdi, Bouazza and Jabur (2015), Adesina (2017), Ojolo and Adeoluwa (2020), who says cybercrime is caused by unemployment.

CONCLUSION

There has been a surge in the number of cyber-crime committed by tertiary students. That many Social Studies students have become more susceptible to cyber-crime-related activities has created significant difficulties for them. Crime diverts students' attention and resources away from more positive uses, which has a negative impact on their learning outcomes.

The study provided empirical evidence on the impact of cyber-crime on students learning outcomes. The study established that a relationship existed between cyber-crime and students learning outcomes. It has been determined that cybercrime has an impact on students because it causes poor performance and malpractice in school examination. Also, the study proved that there is an association between unemployment and cyber-crime.

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The government should provide youth empowerment as a solution to unemployment.
2. The government should implement cyber security best practices, especially in the financial sector.
3. Security software should be installed on personal devices.
4. Universities should introduce cyber security as a compulsory course.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adegbola, I. A., & Fadara, O. O. (2022). Cyber Crime among Mathematical Science Students: Implications on their Academic Performance. *Journal of Digital Learning and Distance Education*, 1(2), 47-54.
- 2) Adeniye, E. O. (2012) Court jails undergraduate over internet fraud in senator Bode Ola's cyber café. <http://www.efccnigeria.org/20i2t.html>
- 3) Adesina, O. S. (2017). Cybercrime and poverty in Nigeria. *Canadian social science*, 13(4), 19-29.
- 4) Ajayi, O. A. (2019). Secondary school students' perceptions of incidences of internet crimes among school age children in Oyo and Ondo States, Nigeria. Unpublished Master dissertation, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- 5) Akinyetun, T. S., Salau, J. A., Bakare, T. O., Ahoton, A. S., Alausa, J. A., & Odeyemi, D. D. (2021). The effect of Covid-19 on youth unemployment, cybercrime and national security in Nigeria: Evidence from Nairaland. *African Journal of Sociological and Psychological Studies*, 1(1), 31-58.
- 6) Akogwo, L. I. (2018). The internet and emergence of yahoo-boys sub-culture in Nigeria. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 2(2), 368-38.
- 7) Al-Barashdi, H. S., Bouazza, A., & Jabur, N. H. (2015). Smartphone addiction among university undergraduates: a literature review. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, 4(3), 210-225.
- 8) Aransiola, J. O., & Asindemade, S. O. (2011). Understanding cybercrime perpetrators and the strategies they employ in Nigeria. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 14(12), 759–763. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2010.0307>.
- 9) Asadu, C. (2021, March 18). *Nigeria ranked 16th in FBI global cybercrime victims report*. The Cable. <https://www.thecable.ng/nigeria-ranked-16th-in-fbi-global-cybercrime-victims-repo-rt>.
- 10) Atubi, O. F. & Obro, S. (2020). Covid-19 pandemic lockdown and the upsurge of online learning: Prospects for social studies in Nigeria. *Journal of the Social Sciences*, 48(3), 4002-4011.
- 11) Ayo, J. (2013) Internet Fleecing Scams Thrive in Nigeria. <http://archives.cnn.ComJ2002 /TECH/ internet/0 8/11 /nigeria.scam/index.html>
- 12) Austin, T. (2013) Leadership through Education. *Positive Leadership Monograph Series No. 12*: Lagos Centre for Social Science Research and Development.
- 13) Edeoghon, I.A. & Mobote, H.E. (2020). Cyber-crime in Nigeria: Sociotechnical Implications, Preventive and Counter Measures. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Isi-Edeoghon/publication/358460184_Cybercrime_in_Nigeria_Sociotechnical_Implications_Preventive_and_Counter_Measures/links/62035eb90445354498d223aa/Cyber-crime-in-Nigeria-Sociotechnical-Implications-Preventive-and-Counter-Measures.pdf.
- 14) Frank, M. (2019). *Nigeria: Sigh in the Dark*. www.alder-consulting.com
- 15) Farris M. Report (2012). *Nigeria: Sigh in the Dark*. www.alder-consulting.com
- 16) Igba, I. D., Igba, E. C., Nwambam, A. S., Nnamani, S. C., Egbe, E. U., & Ogodo, J. V. (2018). Cybercrime among university undergraduates: implications on their academic achievement. *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, 13(2), 1144-1154.
- 17) John, Y. 1. (2016). The New Phenomenon of Phishing, Credit Card Fraud, Identity Theft, Internet Piracy and Nigeria Criminal Law. 3rd Conference on Law and Technology, Faculty of Law, University Kebangsaan, Malaysia and Faculty of Law, University of Tasmania, Australia.
- 18) Khan, M. A., Akram, S., Munir, S., & Almas, I. (2021). Causes and effects of cyber-crime victimization among educated youth: A study of BZU. *IUB Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2), 40-45.
- 19) Lin, T. T., & Chiang, Y. H. (2017). Investigating predictors of smartphone dependency symptoms and effects on academic performance, improper phone use and perceived sociability. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, 15(6), 655-676.
- 20) Monsurat, I. (2020). African insurance (spiritualism) and the success rate of cyber criminals in Nigeria: a study of the yahoo boys in Ilorin, Nigeria. *International Journal of Cyber Criminology*, 14(1), 300-315.
- 21) Obro, S. (2021). The internet and quality social studies education for sustainable development in post-covid-19: A review. *Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengkajian Ilmu Pendidikan: e-Saintika*, 5(1), 15-26.

The Impact of Cybercrime on the Learning Outcomes of Social Studies Undergraduates in Delta State University.

- 22) Onyema, E. M., Ogechukwu, U., & Anthonia, E. C. D. (2019). Potentials of mobile technologies in enhancing the effectiveness of inquiry-based learning approach. *International Journal of Education (IJE)*, 2(01), 1-22.
- 23) Osuji, C. U., & Amadi, J. C. (2020). Global education marketing: using distance learning to export knowledge implications on globalization. *Journal of Education and Entrepreneurship*, 7(1), 14-25.
- 24) Wahab, B. (2017, December 4). LAUTECH has the highest concentration of cybercriminals -DSS. *Pulse Nigeria*. <https://www.pulse.ng/communities/student/ladoke-akintola-university-of-technology-lautech-has-the-highest-concentration-of/3ly2g00>.